

Location

Paris, France (HQ Paris Habitat)

Innovation

Circular Decision-Making for Real Estate Assets

Partners

Delft University of Technology
Paris Habitat

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

The Paris Habitat demonstration applies a participatory, multi-level circular decision-making process developed by TU Delft to guide the renovation and densification of a 1950s social housing complex. The process connects strategic, scenario, and product-level thinking —combining Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis, Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), and Fuzzy-TOPSIS to explore and rank circular renovation pathways. Supported by AI-based visualisation and narratives, it helps align technical, social, and environmental priorities, clarify trade-offs, and extend the use life of real estate assets through a transparent and replicable approach.

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

- › Descriptor-variant tables (excel)
- › Cross-impact matrix (ScenarioWizard)
- › Stakeholder weighting data AHP (excel)
- › Scenario ranking outputs Topsis (excel)
- › AI generated narratives and visuals (ChatGPT-4o / DALL-E image outputs)
- › Building and product data (IFC).

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- › Stakeholder engagement & satisfaction
- › Decision traceability
- › Planning efficiency (time reduction)
- › Scenario consistency score
- › Stakeholder alignment with outcome

IMAGES

Scenario 1: The elevated commons

In the heart of Paris's 20th-century residential belt, a once-underutilized housing block has undergone a bold transformation. No longer just a relic of post-war urban planning, this building now exemplifies a new vision for urban living: socially connected, ecologically rich, and spatially intensified — all while staying aligned with city policy and architectural heritage.

Two new floors rise seamlessly above the original three-story structure, giving the building a renewed verticality without overwhelming its surroundings. The added levels are constructed using lightweight prefabricated elements clad in vertical timber slats — a nod to contemporary sustainability while maintaining harmony with the existing geometry. The result is a striking hybrid of past and future, showing how densification can be spatially elegant and context-aware.

This vertical expansion made it possible to introduce a more diverse housing supply, with various apartment sizes, layouts, and access points. Façade rhythm subtly changes, reflecting the heterogeneity inside — balconies vary in form and depth, offering views and privacy to a broader spectrum of residents. Despite the project going slightly over budget, the investment was deliberate, channeling resources into features that elevate both form and function.

The transformation unfolds most visibly at ground level. What was once a narrow strip of underutilized greenery has blossomed into a lush landscape, with native shrubs, vertical green façades, and a pocket park that includes community seating, play areas, and bike infrastructure. These improvements have catalyzed social cohesion, fostering spontaneous encounters between neighbors and intergenerational use of space.

A large canopy at the entrance provides shelter and a sense of arrival, now flanked by clear municipal signage indicating alignment with Paris's urban policy and renovation goals. Despite modest energy performance gains (the building now meets Label C), the focus was broader: ensuring a medium reduction in environmental impact through material choices and waste minimization.

Inside, residents benefit from small improvements in comfort and limited internal upgrades — minor but noticeable. Operable windows, new blinds, and occasional flowering pots hint at a subtle elevation in daily quality of life.

Together, these elements compose a coherent urban narrative: one where density becomes opportunity, greenery becomes community, and design becomes dialogue — not only between old and new, but between people and place.

Descriptors

	Energy Performance	Energy Label C	
	Environmental Impact	Medium Impact	
	Densification	2 Floor addition	
	Green Spaces	High addition	
	Services & Outdoor Spaces	Big Improvement	
	Quality of Use	Small Improvement	
	Indoor Comfort	Low - small upgrade	
	Diversification	Diverse housing supply	
	Cost	A little over budget	
	Social Cohesion	High social Impact	
	Marketing & City Policy	In accordance with plans	

CONTACTS

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